

The Relationship between Social Competence, Heresy, and School Welfare: The Mediating Role of Adolescents' Emotional and Moral Maturity in Schools

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Abstract

The outline of student achievement blueprints includes several elements of personality, spirituality, and ethics that are potentially influential in student achievement; In this regard, we can mention meritocracy, heresy, and moral and emotional maturity. The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between social competence, heresy, and school welfare: the mediating role of adolescents' emotional and moral maturity in schools. The method of this research is descriptive-correlational. The study population consists of all high school students in Tehran in the academic year 1398. The research sample was 600 (250 boys and 350 girls) high school students in Tehran who were selected by multi-stage cluster sampling. Students answered the questionnaires of Kaplan and Maher School Welfare Scale (1999), Singh and Bahargava (1990) emotional maturity, Manavipour students' moral development (2012), and Ebrahimi's apocalyptic test (2011), Merit Perception (Harter, 1982). After data collection, they were analyzed using Spss-22 and Amos-21 software and Pearson correlation coefficient and structural equations. The assumed model was fitting in the research community. The results of the analysis showed that the mediating role of moral and emotional maturity in the relationship between heresy and perception of school competence and well-being is positive and significant and the proposed model explains 65% of the variance in students' school well-being. Based on the research findings, it was found that the effect of heresy and perception of competence is indirect rather than direct and through moral and emotional maturity. As a result, students' moral and emotional maturity and well-being increase with increasing perceptions of competence and heresy.

Perception of the afterlife's moral maturity's emotional maturity welfare school